

1 Despite mixing, sediment accumulation governs the resolution of
2 the sedimentary record: Supplementary information

3 Niklas Hohmann^{1*}, Emilia Jarochovska¹

4 ¹Department of Earth Sciences, Utrecht University, 3584 CB Utrecht, The Netherlands

5 *Corresponding author, email: N.H.Hohmann@uu.nl

6 **MODEL DESCRIPTION**

7 We model the joint distribution of particle ages and depths via the diffusion-advection
8 equation

9
$$\frac{\partial}{\partial a} u(a, d) = \frac{\partial}{\partial d} \left(D_b(d) \frac{\partial}{\partial d} u(a, d) - Su(a, d) \right) \text{ (Supp. Eq. 1, Eq. 1)}$$

10 where a is particle age, d is depth below the sediment-water interface, $u(a, d)$ is the density
11 of particles of age a at depth d , S is sediment accumulation rate, and D_b is the depth-
12 dependent biodiffusion coefficient (compare Figure 1 B in main text). The model is defined
13 for $a \geq 0$ and $0 \leq d \leq d_{max}$, where d_{max} is a depth large enough for $D_b(d)$ to drop to
14 zero. We use boundary condition

15
$$u(0, d) = f(d) \text{ (Supp. Eq. 2)}$$

16 with an arbitrary function f that describes the depth at which particles of age 0 are placed in
17 the sediment. In addition, we assume no particle flux through the sediment-water interface:

18
$$D_b(d) \frac{\partial}{\partial d} u(a, d) - Su(a, d) = 0 \text{ (Supp. Eq. 3)}$$

19 at $d = 0$. No boundary condition is enforced at the bottom of the system d_{max} , as $D_b(d)$ is
20 assumed to eventually drop to 0. This makes the bottom the downwind side of a pure

21 advection equation for which no boundary condition is required. See Hohmann (2024) for a
 22 derivation of this model from the classic Guinasso and Schink (1975) model, see Terry and
 23 Novak (2015) for a similar model in cave environments.

24 We assume biodiffusion D_b is constant within a surface mixed layer (SML) of thickness L
 25 and drops to 0 below it. We rescale the system using mixing depth L as characteristic length
 26 unit and L/S (transit time of particles through the SML due to sediment accumulation) as
 27 characteristic time unit. The re-scaled system $\tilde{u}(a, d)$ is fully characterized by the
 28 dimensionless mixing intensity (inverse Péclet number)

$$29 \quad G = \frac{D_b}{L \cdot S} \text{ (Supp. Eq. 4, Eq. 2)}$$

30 (Guinasso and Schink 1975a). Let $f_{avg}(a) = \tilde{u}(a, 1)$ be the distribution of particle ages at the
 31 bottom of the SML in the rescaled system \tilde{u} . Below the SML, the system is purely advective
 32 with advection velocity of 1, making the age-depth distribution $\tilde{u}(a, d)$ a translation of f_{avg} :

$$33 \quad \tilde{u}(a, d) = f_{avg}(a-d) \text{ (Supp. Eq. 5)}$$

34 reflecting that per depth increment, the particle cohort ages by one time increment
 35 (Supplementary Figure 1). For a particle cohort of age \tilde{a} that is old enough for all particles to
 36 have left the SML, the stratigraphic position of particles is given by

$$37 \quad f_{dis}(d) = \tilde{u}(\tilde{a}, d) = f_{avg}(\tilde{a}-d) \text{ (Supp. Eq. 6)}$$

38 (Supplementary Figure 1). We measure time-averaging avg and stratigraphic disorder
 39 $disord$ using the interquartile range (IQR) of particle ages and depths, respectively
 40 (Tomašových et al. 2018; Berensmeier et al. 2023). Because of the translation invariance of
 41 the IQR, both time-averaging and stratigraphic disorder are identical in the dimensionless
 42 system and uniquely determined by G (compare Rooze et al. (2023)). Let F_{mix} be the function

43 that specifies the dimensionless time-averaging and disorder as a function of mixing
44 intensity:

$$45 \quad F_{mix}(G) = IQR(f_{avg}) = IQR(f_{dis}). \quad (Supp. Eq. 7)$$

46 Reversing the scaling, we get the expressions

$$47 \quad tavg(S, D_b, L) = F_{mix}(G) \cdot \frac{L}{S} \quad (Supp. Eq. 8)$$

48 and

$$49 \quad disord(S, D_b, L) = F_{mix}(G) \cdot L \quad (Supp. Eq. 9)$$

50 for time-averaging and stratigraphic disorder (Eq. 3 in main text), yielding the relation

$$51 \quad tavg \cdot S = disord \quad (Supp. Eq. 10)$$

52 between the two (Eq. 4 in main text). Values of F_{mix} were calculated using Matlab (MATLAB
53 R2025b) for values of G between 10^{-3} and 10^5 , see Figure 2 in main text. As initial age
54 distribution, we use the function

$$55 \quad f(d) = \frac{2}{\epsilon\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \exp\left(\left(\frac{-0.5d}{\epsilon}\right)^2\right) \quad (Supp. Eq. 11)$$

56 with $\epsilon = 0.005$, approximating a unit pulse of particles of age 0 introduced at the sediment
57 surface. All code is available in (Hohmann 2026).

58 Note that the derived equations are unsuitable to examine the transition from an unmixed
59 (Precambrian) SML to a Phanerozoic SML, as this represents a qualitative rather than a
60 quantitative difference. Mathematically, this transition is a singular perturbation and results
61 across it will depend on the exact balance between biodiffusion and mixing depth and their
62 temporal development.

63 Our model assumptions of constant sediment accumulation, biodiffusion, and mixing depth
64 reflect data availability from compilations of empirical measurements and the standard
65 approaches used to estimate SML parameters from tracer profiles. While there are multiple
66 global compilations of individual SML parameters available (e.g., Song et al. (2022); Solan et
67 al. (2019)), we use a compilation containing all three parameters of interest measured at the
68 same location to avoid propagation of extrapolation effects into our results (Hohmann 2022).
69 We hypothesize that episodic sediment accumulation will reduce time-averaging and disorder
70 by removing particles from the SML faster, thus reducing their exposure to mixing (Sadler
71 1993). Deep mixing below the recognized mixing depth will, however, increase time-
72 averaging (Tomašových et al. 2023) and, as a result, stratigraphic disorder.

73 Many models of particle mixing and its effect on earth science signals are available in the
74 scientific literature, allowing for modeling of complex depth- and time-dependent dynamics
75 (see e.g., Meysman et al. (2010)). The majority of SML parameters are estimated by fitting
76 tracer profiles predicted by the Guinasso and Schink (1975) model to empirical observations
77 (e.g., DeMaster and Cochran (1982)). As the diffusion-advection model used here is also
78 derived from the Guinasso and Schink model, it minimizes discrepancies between inference
79 and prediction models while remaining simple enough to provide analytical insights into the
80 connection between particle age and depth (e.g., Equations 3 and 4 in the main text).

81 Biodiffusion can be anisotropic (Wheatcroft 1991), spatially heterogeneous (Zuhr et al. 2022)
82 and size-dependent (Wheatcroft and Jumars 1987; Shull and Yasuda 2001; Hupp et al. 2019;
83 Hupp and Kelly 2020) due to ecological preferences of bioturbators and physical effects such
84 as granular convection (Savranskaia et al. 2022). Higher biodiffusion coefficients have been
85 observed in the fine particle fraction (Wheatcroft and Jumars 1987), suggesting that time-
86 averaging and disorder might be reduced for large particles. However, it is common to
87 observe high values of stratigraphic disorder and age-homogenization across multiple

88 decimeters for large shells (fraction > 4 mm) (Kosnik et al. 2007, 2009; Dominguez et al.
89 2016; Tomašových et al. 2018). This suggests that while mixing intensity of large particles is
90 high enough for our results to be valid for large size fractions, the exact values of time-
91 averaging and stratigraphic disorder might vary across size fractions.

92 Destruction of particles in the taphonomic active zone (Davies et al. 1989) reduces time-
93 averaging (Kowalewski 1996; Olszewski 2004; Kowalewski et al. 2017), and, as a result,
94 stratigraphic disorder. Our model does not incorporate particle destruction, as the taphonomic
95 half-life of particles encapsulates age- and taxon-dependent dissolution of (bio)minerals,
96 sequestration, and loss of taxonomically identifiable features and is accordingly difficult to
97 constrain (Davies et al. 1989; Meldahl et al. 1997; Kidwell et al. 2005; Tomašových et al.
98 2014; Kowalewski et al. 2017; Nawrot et al. 2022). Our estimates are applicable to particles
99 with a taphonomic half-life longer than the particle residence time in the taphonomically
100 active zone (Delhez and Deleersnijder 2012). Especially in deep-sea environments with very
101 high predicted values of time-averaging, taphonomic half-life will become a limiting factor
102 (Kuderer and Middelburg 2024). Particle destruction will also reduce sample size, increasing
103 the effects of random fluctuations (Olszewski 2004). However, the interquartile range is
104 robust to outliers, reducing the effect of small sample sizes and reworking of exceptionally
105 old particles.

106

107 *Supplementary Figure 1: Conceptual representation for the argument that disorder and time-*
 108 *averaging are identical in the rescaled system: age-depth distribution of particles in the*
 109 *dimensionless system (A), with the distribution of particle depths of one age cohort f_{dis} (B)*
 110 *and age distribution of particles below the surface mixed layer f_{avg} (C). Because the*
 111 *advection velocity below the SLM is 1, transects along the depth- and age axes are identical*
 112 *up to translation.*

113 **OVERVIEW OF PARAMETERS FROM THE SMLBase**

114

115 *Supplementary Figure 2: Histograms of sediment accumulation rate (A), biodiffusion (B),*
 116 *and mixing depth (C) from the SMLBase (Hohmann 2022) that inform the model. Panel (D)*
 117 *shows the distribution of F_{mix} (see Supp. Eq. 7) calculated for the entries in the SMLBase.*
 118 *F_{mix} clusters in saturated environments, with a median of 1.078. A total of 287 simultaneous*
 119 *co-located measurements are included in the SMLBase.*

120

121 **RESULTS OF REGRESSION ANALYSES**

122 **SML Parameters Against Time-Averaging and Stratigraphic Disorder**

		Time-averaging				
	Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	Partial R ²
Not normalized	Intercept	-0.032	0.008	-3.861	0.00014	NA
	$\log_{10}(S)$	-1.057	0.004	-248.247	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	0.995
	$\log_{10}(D_b)$	0.063	0.003	19.406	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	0.569
	$\log_{10}(L)$	0.931	0.008	120.296	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	0.981
Normalized	$\log_{10}(S)$	-0.991	0.004	-248.247	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	NA
	$\log_{10}(D_b)$	0.078	0.004	19.406	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	NA
	$\log_{10}(L)$	0.326	0.003	120.296	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	NA

123 *Supplementary Table 1: Estimates of regression coefficients and their associated standard*
 124 *errors, t values, p-values, and partial R² for time averaging from raw data (top) and*
 125 *normalized data (standardized regression coefficients, bottom). Sample size is n = 287. No*
 126 *partial R² are given for the normalized GLM as they are identical to the original GLM.*
 127 *Multicollinearity is weak in all GLMs, with variance inflation factors (VIFs) below 3. See*
 128 *Supplementary Figure 2 A, B for coefficient plots.*

129

		Stratigraphic disorder				
	Coefficient	Estimate	Std. error	t value	Pr(> t)	partial R ²
Not normalized	Intercept	-0.032	0.008	-3.861	0.00014	NA
	log ₁₀ (S)	-0.057	0.004	-13.386	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	0.386
	log ₁₀ (D _b)	0.063	0.003	19.406	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	0.569
	log ₁₀ (L)	0.931	0.008	120.296	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	0.981
Normalized	log ₁₀ (S)	-0.155	0.012	-13.386	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	NA
	log ₁₀ (D _b)	0.227	0.012	19.406	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	NA
	log ₁₀ (L)	0.949	0.008	120.296	< 10 ⁻¹⁶	NA

130 *Supplementary Table 2: Estimates of regression coefficients and their associated standard*
131 *errors, t values, p-values, and partial R² for stratigraphic disorder from raw data (top) and*
132 *normalized data (standardized regression coefficients, bottom). Sample size is n = 287. No*
133 *partial R² are given for the normalized GLM as they are identical to the original GLM.*
134 *Multicollinearity is weak in all GLMs, with variance inflation factors (VIFs) below 3. See*
135 *Supplementary Figure 2 C, D for coefficient plots.*

136 Because of the analytical connection between dependent variables (Equation 8 and Figure 2
137 in main text), partial R² and slope of mixing depth and biodiffusion are identical in both
138 GLMs (Figure 4 B, C, E, F). Sediment accumulation rate has the strongest influence on time-
139 averaging (partial R² 0.995, slope -1.057), followed by mixing depth (partial R² 0.981, slope
140 0.931), with only intermediate to weak influence of biodiffusion (partial R² 0.569, slope
141 0.063). As sediment accumulation rate has both the largest slope and its spans four orders of
142 magnitude, its influence on time-averaging dominates that of mixing depth (Figure 4 A).
143 Sediment accumulation rate has only a weak influence on stratigraphic disorder (partial R²
144 0.386, slope -0.057), making mixing depth the dominant control of stratigraphic disorder
145 (Figure 4 E).

146

147 *Supplementary Figure 3: Regression coefficients (first column, A and C) and standardized*
 148 *regression coefficients (second column, B and D) for the relationship between sediment*
 149 *accumulation rate S, biodiffusion D_b , and mixing depth L and time-averaging (first row, A*
 150 *and B) and stratigraphic disorder (C and D).*

151 **Water Depth Against Time-Averaging and Stratigraphic Disorder**

Formula	Coefficient	Estimate	Std. error	T value	Pr(> t)
$\log_{10}(avg) \sim \log_{10}(wd)$	Intercept	0.0955	0.1760	0.544	5.87e-1
	$\log_{10}(wd)$	0.7530	0.0664	11.300	8.09e-25
$\log_{10}(disorder) \sim \log_{10}(wd)$	Intercept	1.0200	0.0718	14.10	9.05 e-35
	$\log_{10}(wd)$	-0.0763	0.271	-2.81	5.29 e-3

152 *Supplementary Table 3: Estimates of regression coefficients and their associated standard*
 153 *errors, t values, and p-values for the water depth dependency of time-averaging and*
 154 *stratigraphic disorder. Sample size is n=287.*

155 Because sediment accumulation rate decreases with water depth, time-averaging increases
 156 with water depth, with values above 10 000 years at depths below 1000 m (Figure 5 A). In

157 contrast, stratigraphic disorder decreases slightly with water depth, as mixing depth does not
158 depend on water depth (Boudreau 1998; Teal et al. 2008) (Figure 5 B).

159 **FITTING THE DIFFUSION-ADVECTION MODEL TO EMPIRICAL AGE-DEPTH** 160 **DISTRIBUTIONS**

161 For Figure 1 B in the main text, the diffusion-advection model (Eq. 1 in main text) was
162 visually fit to the empirical distribution of particle ages (Figure 1 A). Particle destruction was
163 assumed to be negligible and the sediment accumulation rate of 2.2 cm/y determined by
164 Tomašových et al. (2018) was used. We assumed a surface mixed layer with constant
165 biodiffusion from 0 to 17 cm depth, a thin layer from 17 to 18 cm depth where biodiffusion
166 linearly drops, an extended deep mixing layer from 18 cm to 120 cm depth with constant
167 biodiffusion, and a linear drop to no biodiffusion from 120 cm to 125 cm depth. Biodiffusion
168 coefficient values where the modeled age-depth distribution best fit the empirical
169 observations were 780 cm²/y in the surface mixed layer and 20 cm²/y in the deep mixed layer.
170 Mathematically, this could be made rigorous, e.g., by minimizing the offset between the
171 empirical cumulative distribution of particle ages and the cumulative distribution function of
172 particle ages predicted by the diffusion-advection model. This would result in minimizing

$$173 \quad f(p) = \sum_{\text{sediment layers } i} \sum_{a_i \text{ in layer } i} |F_i(a_i) - C_{p,i}(a_i)|$$

174 where

- 175 • p are the model parameters of the diffusion-advection model
- 176 • a_i are the particle ages in sediment layer i
- 177 • F_i is the (empirical) cumulative distribution function of particle ages in sediment
178 layer i

179 • $C_{p,i}$ is the cumulative distribution function of particle ages in sediment layer i
180 predicted by the diffusion-advection model with parameters p .

181 However, solving this optimization problem is beyond the scope of this paper.

182 **CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY**

183 All code required to reproduce the results is available under

184 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20813310> (Hohmann 2026).

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